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Review Article

A Review on Artificial Intelligence (AI) In Drug Product Designing, Development and Manufacturing

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ABSTRACT

The pharmaceutical industry is increasingly leveraging advanced AI technologies to address its most pressing challenges. Artificial intelligence (AI) is used to automate tasks traditionally reliant on human intelligence, such as optimizing process design and control, smart monitoring and maintenance, and trend monitoring. AI can also predict pharmacokinetics, enhancing the effectiveness and affordability of drug research through computer modeling. AI technology development can be divided into two main categories: traditional computational methods and systems that utilize artificial neural networks (ANNs) to simulate brain functions. Machine learning algorithms have been employed by Novartis to anticipate themes that are not previously identified but could be worthy of further study, speeding up the screening process. Leading biopharmaceutical businesses are using AI to improve patient outcomes through mobile platforms and drug discovery. The evolving pharmaceutical field has always focused on small-molecule pharmaceuticals with three intrinsic qualities: stability, adequate potency for therapeutic applications, and acceptable toxicity for the majority of users. Artificial intelligence applications in medication delivery and nanotechnology have been driving forces behind the biotech and pharmaceutical industries. Quality-by-design R&D has been crucial to the modern pharmaceutical evolution toward better drug delivery. AI can enhance nanosystem design by facilitating a better understanding of the biological environment, allowing pharmaceutical items to be nanoengineered. In formulation, neural networks with a hidden layer were found to be effective in predicting drug release. In product development, the expandability of neural networks makes them suitable for resolving issues with establishing quality in the manufacturing of consumer goods.

INTRODUCTION

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Pharmaceutical manufacturing is a highly complex process that involves the interaction of multiple variables, including process conditions and raw materials, which play a critical role in shaping the quality of the final product. This complexity has driven researchers to adopt Design of Experiment (DoE) methods to connect Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) with process parameters, as well as the characteristics of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and excipients, in order to define the design space.[1] The pharmaceutical industry is undergoing significant changes, facing challenges such as the need to speed up production processes to meet demand while staying competitive globally. Additionally, there is a push to integrate Process Analytical Technology (PAT) and Quality by Design (QbD) principles into both analytical and process development to comply with the guidelines set by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA).[2] Statistical tools and concepts have been successfully applied in various sectors, such as the automobile and chemical industries, but the pharmaceutical industry presents distinct challenges. While these tools have proven effective elsewhere, the pharmaceutical sector is exploring innovative strategies to leverage advanced AI technologies to address some of its most pressing issues. In this context, AI in the pharmaceutical industry refers to the use of algorithms that automate tasks traditionally reliant on human intelligence.[3]

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a technology with numerous applications in both everyday life and business. AI offers many possibilities in the pharmaceutical industry, including but not limited to optimizing process design and process control, smart monitoring and maintenance, and trend monitoring to drive continuous improvement. [4] The use of AI to support pharmaceutical manufacturing can be deployed with other advanced manufacturing technologies to achieve desired benefits. [5] In recent years, the

pharmaceutical industry has adopted innovative AI tools to address some of its most pressing challenges.[6] AI in medicine involves using automated algorithms to complete tasks typically dependent on human intelligence. Information models can also be used to assess in vivo responses, evaluate therapeutic drugs, and identify the most suitable medications. AI can also predict pharmacokinetics, enhancing the effectiveness and affordability of drug research through computer modeling.

AI technology development can be divided into two main categories. The first involves traditional computational methods, where experts like mechanical engineers replicate human experience and analyze the results. The second category focuses on systems that utilize artificial neural networks (ANNs) to simulate brain functions. Specifically, various neural networks, including deep neural networks (DNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), play a critical role in advancing AI technology. [7]

DRUG DISCOVERY

DRUG AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Testing the medicine against illness patterns often takes a long period. It takes further investigation to identify molecules that are intriguing and deserving of additional research. The Novartis research team employed machine learning algorithms to anticipate themes that were not previously identified but could be worthy of more study, which sped up the screening process. New pharmaceuticals can be given more rapidly and at a lower labor cost since computers are faster at finding new information than human screening and laboratory testing. This is because computer-aided research guidance for each compound is less expensive. [8]

Leading biopharmaceutical businesses currently use AI to improve patient outcomes in the following ways: [9]

[a] Mobile platforms to improve health outcomes — allows patients to agree by inputting real-time information.

[b] Drug Discovery: Software firms and pharmaceutical corporations are collaborating to evaluate the application of technology in the pricy and time-consuming drug discovery process.

- **Process Optimization:** AI algorithms analyze vast amounts of data from production processes to identify patterns and optimize manufacturing conditions. This helps in improving yields, reducing waste, and minimizing downtime.

- **Quality Control:** AI is used to monitor production in real time, ensuring that products meet quality standards. Machine learning models can detect deviations in quality early, preventing defects and ensuring consistency in the final product.

- **Predictive Maintenance:** AI predicts when machinery and equipment need maintenance, reducing the likelihood of unexpected breakdowns and ensuring continuous production. This predictive capability improves overall efficiency and lowers

CLASSIFICATION OF AI [10,11,12]

AI can be classified in two ways: based on its capabilities and based on its presence.

According to its capabilities:

- Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI) or Weak AI: Designed for specific tasks like facial recognition, driving a car, playing chess, or managing traffic signals.
- Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) or Strong AI: Comparable to human intelligence, AGI can perform any intellectual task a human can and handle unfamiliar tasks.
- Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI): Far surpassing human intelligence, ASI can outperform humans in fields like art, mathematics, and space exploration.

According to its presence:

- Type 1 (Reactive Machines): These systems are designed for narrow tasks and cannot learn from past experiences. They lack memory. An example is IBM's chess program, which recognizes pieces and predicts moves but cannot improve over time.
- Type 2 (Limited Memory Systems): These AI systems can use past experiences to make decisions, such as in autonomous vehicles. While they learn from recorded observations, the information isn't permanently stored.
- Type 3 (Theory of Mind): This type refers to AI that could understand human emotions, thoughts, and intentions. However, this kind of AI doesn't exist yet.
- Type 4 (Self-Awareness): AI with self-awareness and consciousness, which also does not currently exist.

IDEA OF AI IN PHARMA IS SUITABLE

New technology can help the pharmaceutical sector change. The most creative solution that comes to mind is artificial intelligence, which is the creation of computer systems that are capable of doing tasks like speech recognition, visual perception, decision-making, and translation that normally need human intelligence. As of 2011, IBM estimated that the healthcare industry has 161 billion gigabytes of data. Despite the massive volume of data in this industry, artificial intelligence can assist by analyzing the data and producing insights. support your decision-making, help save lives, and save labor, time, and money.[13] Pandemic prediction: By utilizing artificial intelligence and machine learning, it can examine social media, learn from previous occurrences, and forecast the location and timing of the event with a high degree of accuracy. Apart from the above-described scenarios, there exist numerous other options such as tailoring the therapeutic regimen and creating novel instruments for physicians and patients. Clinical trial research is the process of recruiting trial

participants by using predictive analytics to social media and medical visits.[14]

Handling and Organizing Rare Illnesses AI developments and a resurgence of interest in treating rare diseases. Presently, over 350 million individuals globally are afflicted with over 7,000 uncommon illnesses. But there is hope for those suffering from uncommon diseases: the British biotech startup Heal has raised \$10 billion in Series A funding to create new medications for these illnesses. Another Swiss biotech business, Thera Chon, has raised \$60 million to pursue the development of artificial intelligence-based medications for uncommon genetic illnesses.[15]

AI TO FORECASE NEW MEDICATIONS

Verge tackles challenging issues in drug discovery through data collection and analysis. In order to find hundreds of genes that are challenging to research in brain illnesses like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, or amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, they employ an algorithmic technique. According to The Verge, genetic data collecting and analysis will benefit the drug discovery process, beginning with preclinical trials.[16] The concept is that Verge can monitor, beginning in the pre-clinical phase, how specific medication treatments affect the human brain through artificial intelligence. In order for pharmaceutical corporations to acquire additional knowledge about how medications affect the human brain as quickly as possible. Verge use artificial intelligence to track, with a particular emphasis on the preclinical stage, how various treatments affect the human brain.[17]

USE OF AI IN MEDICAL PRODUCT AND IN MEDICAL PRODUCTS DEVELOPMENT

• Fostering Collaboration to Protect Public Health [18,19]

The FDA's medical product Centers actively collaborate with developers, patient groups, academic institutions, global regulators, and other stakeholders to promote a patient-centered regulatory framework that emphasizes

cooperation and health equity. The Agency aims to address AI-related topics in medical products, such as transparency, explainability, governance, bias, cybersecurity, and quality control. Additionally, they intend to develop educational programs to help regulatory bodies, healthcare professionals, patients, researchers, and industry safely and responsibly navigate the use of AI in medical products. International collaboration will be encouraged to establish global standards and guidelines.

• Advancing Regulatory Approaches to Foster Innovation [20,21]

FDA's medical product Centers aim to create policies that provide clear regulatory guidance for AI use, reinforcing their commitment to public health protection and innovation. This includes monitoring emerging trends and identifying knowledge gaps in regulatory submissions, as well as developing methodologies to assess AI algorithms, mitigate bias, and ensure the resilience of AI systems in adapting to changing clinical inputs and environments. The Centers will continue evaluating AI applications in medical product development and manufacturing.

• Promoting Standards, Guidelines, Best Practices, and Tools for the Medical Product Life Cycle [22]

The FDA's medical product Centers remain committed to upholding safety and effectiveness standards for AI-enabled medical products. Building on Good Machine Learning Practice principles, the Agency plans to refine and develop criteria for evaluating the safe, ethical, and responsible use of AI throughout the medical product life cycle. Additionally, they will promote best practices for the long-term monitoring of the safety and real-world performance of AI-driven medical products.

• Supporting Research for AI Evaluation and Monitoring [23]

To better understand AI's impact on the safety and effectiveness of medical products, the Centers will, subject to available resources, support demonstration projects. These projects will address health inequities associated with AI use in medical product development, promoting equity and ensuring diverse and representative data. Monitoring AI tools in these projects will help ensure compliance with standards and maintain performance and reliability throughout their life cycle.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs)

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) can be utilized for both qualitative and quantitative analysis, particularly in multivariate calibration of data related to active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) and raw materials using advanced analytical techniques like chromatography and spectroscopy. This analysis aids in the identification and determination of APIs within complex mixtures.[24] In pharmaceuticals, the crystalline form, purity, and stability of APIs impact key properties such as solubility, shelf-life, bioavailability, density, and vapor pressure. As a result, various methods have been explored to effectively identify and analyze different crystalline forms within compound mixtures.[25] Research has shown that neural networks can be applied to quantify, characterize, and identify the crystalline forms of drugs based on data generated from modern techniques such as Raman spectroscopy, DRIFT spectral patterns, attenuated total reflectance (FTIR), and X-ray diffraction patterns. [26] Using neural network models, it was demonstrated that signals produced by these analytical methods are proportional to the quantity of crystalline forms in a sample. These ANN models simplify complex processes, making them easier to perform.[27]

ANN models have also been successfully applied to various analytical techniques, including high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), UV-

visible spectrophotometry, and fluorescence spectra. One study used ANN in HPLC for response-surface modeling to separate methyclothiazide and amiloride, where methanol percentage and pH were the input variables, and the capacity factor was the output [28]. The analysis was conducted using two methods: neural network-based analysis (via backpropagation) and regression analysis. The study found that the predicted output responses from ANN models were more accurate than those from regression analysis.[29]

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN DRUG DELIVERY AND PHARMACEUTICAL DEVELOPMENT ITS APPLICATIONS

• The evolving pharmaceutical field [30,31,32]

The development of small-molecule pharmaceuticals with three intrinsic qualities—stability, adequate potency for therapeutic applications, and acceptable toxicity for the vast majority of users—has always been the focus of the pharmaceutical industry, which has always been a conservative one. The most effective type of research and development is the systematic chemical screening of molecular variations in combinatorial libraries, with the goal of creating new compounds with beneficial qualities for application in medicine.

• Drug delivery and nanotechnology [33,34]

Pharmacological build-up at the site of action is a typical goal of pharmacological delivery. Artificial intelligence applications in medication delivery and pharmaceutical development 89 genetic engineering of cells to generate premium biomolecules on a large scale have been the driving forces behind the biotech and pharmaceutical industries.

• Quality-by-design R&D [35,36]

The transition from a methodical series of attempts (a "Trial and Error" technique) to a quality-based rational engineering based on scientific principles

(referred to as QbD) has been crucial to the modern pharmaceutical evolution toward better drug delivery. The foundation for determining the qualities needed to achieve this goal is acquired knowledge. To achieve the QTPP, critical quality attributes (CQAs) are defined. The words "critical process parameters" and "critical material attributes" (CMAs) refer to certain characteristics of the process and the material that have a direct or indirect impact on the CQAs. These variables and characteristics are controlled by the manufacturing control programs.

- **Modeling medication distribution using artificial intelligence [37]**

Artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance nanosystem design by facilitating a better understanding of the biological environment. Medicinal items can then be nanoengineered using this understanding. For drug delivery reasons, the complex system that is the human body is sometimes simplified to a compartmentalized system divided by biological membranes. The concept of biological membranes describes the physicochemical properties of the barriers that separate different biological compartments, categorizing a wide variety of environments and epithelia.

- **In Formulation: Controlled Release Tablets [38,39]**

In various studies, they simulated the in vitro release properties of different drugs incorporated into matrices made from various hydrophilic polymers. Across all cases, neural networks with a hidden layer were found to be effective in predicting drug release. Neural networks were used to create three-dimensional plots of factors such as massing time, compression pressure, crushing strength, and drug release. The goal was to optimize tablet strength and choose the most suitable lubricant. Although trends were identified, no optimal formulations were provided. The trends produced by neural networks were

similar to those generated through statistical approaches. Similar neural network models were developed and further optimized using genetic algorithms. The findings showed that the ideal formulation depends on the materials used and the relative importance of the output parameters. High tablet strength and low friability were only achievable at the cost of longer burst times. In all cases, lactose was identified as the preferred diluent, and fluidized bed granulation was the favored technology.

- **In the development of products: [40,41]**

Medicine's advancement is an optimization problem. It entails optimizing several formulas and methodologies. The expandability of neural networks is one of its main advantages. These characteristics make them appropriate for resolving issues with establishing quality in the manufacturing of consumer goods. For product quantity development, the ANN model is suggested because of its adaptability and predictive power when analyzing the impact of several elements (like formulation and compression parameters) on tablet goods (like dissolving). In a downsizing experiment, artificial neural networks offer a helpful tool for developing medicine delivery based on microemulsions.

- **Artificial intelligence application in pharmaceutical product R&D[42,43]**

There are two primary stages to the research and development process: the early and late phases. Early stage research and development consists of converting an idea into a design and creating a prototype that is tested while taking the fictitious mechanism of action as specified during the preliminary phases of study. This is integrated into the prototype and continuously improved during prototype testing. Early evidence of safety and efficacy is required, particularly for novel pharmaceutical entities and consumer goods. The improvement in the later stages is more convincing in terms of the scalability and resilience of the real

manufacturing process, as the more research and development can be enabled by the capacity to create the targeted pharmaceutical goods in greater quantities at a specified quality chance. The focus of late development is not limited to this genuinely extends to the product life cycle management, but is regarded as one of the most important elements.

CONCLUSION

AI is being applied in various aspects of the pharmaceutical industry, including drug delivery, nanotechnology, formulation, product development, and product life cycle management. By leveraging AI technologies, the pharmaceutical industry can overcome its challenges and improve patient outcomes.

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